

Synthesis of 3,4,5-Triphenyloxazine-2-ones

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3,4,5-Triphenyloxazine-2-ones have been prepared starting from benzoin and phenyl isocyanate in the presence of triethylamine. All the compounds were obtained in good yields

MOST of the reactions of isocyanates involve the formation of widely differing cyclic and acyclic reaction products¹. The reactions of isocyanates, such as formation of ureas², oxazines³, imidazoles⁴, carbodiimides⁵ and oligodimerisation⁶ are of industrial importance. A wide variety of functionally differing compounds can be synthesised by the condensation of hydroxy aldehydes or ketones and isocyanates^{7,8}.

- (1) R=H
(2) R=-COOH,
(3) R=-NHCO₂H₃

Dimer (4)

Experimental

Physical constants yields and analytical values of compounds are reported in Table 1. Melting points were determined using a Thomas Hoover capillary melting point apparatus which was calibrated against known standards. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Baird 455 double beam spectrograph

using KBr pellets. The nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. Tlc was carried out on silica gel with isopropanol as the eluent. The chromatogram was developed by exposing tlc plates to iodine vapours.

Preparation of 1 : A solution of benzoin (4.25 g, 1 mol) of anhydrous benzene (10 ml) was added with constant stirring to a solution of phenyl isocyanate (2.60 ml, 1 mol) and triethylamine (0.5 ml) in benzene (10 ml) over a period of 30 min. The reaction was exothermic resulting in the formation of white crystals. After the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and allowed to stand overnight, the crude product was obtained which on recrystallisation with benzene gave pure product (1). The yield of the product was almost quantitative. Ir spectrum of 1 showed peaks at 3 400 (broad band) (OH) and 1 750 cm⁻¹ (C=O). The nmr spectrum showed two singlet at δ 6.15 and 1.8 corresponding to benzylic and hydroxy protons. The presence of hydroxy group in 1 is also confirmed by preparation of its characteristic acetyl derivative (2).

Preparation of 3 : The compound of the type 3 was obtained by reacting benzoin (2.12 g, 1 mol) and phenyl isocyanate (2.60 ml, 2 mol) in the presence of triethylamine (0.5 ml) in dry benzene. The white crystals obtained were recrystallised from ethanol. Ir spectrum of 3 showed peaks at 3 360-3 395 (double peak) (NH) and 1 765 cm⁻¹ (C=O). A singlet was observed at δ 6.9 ppm of benzylic proton in the nmr spectrum.

TABLE 1

Compd.	M p °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
1	143	55.50	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	76.13 (76.93)	5.15 (5.18)	4.20 (4.28)
2	153	39.50	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ NO ₄	76.55 (76.65)	5.20 (5.27)	3.78 (3.90)
3	160	50.00	C ₃₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄	74.40 (74.60)	4.56 (4.88)	6.15 (6.22)
4	180	43.75	C ₃₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅	77.45 (77.58)	4.85 (4.92)	4.24 (4.26)

Preparation of 4 : The Dimer (4) was formed from benzoin (4.12 ml, 2 mol) and phenyl isocyanate (1.3 ml, 1 mol) and triethylamine (0.5 ml). The product purified from benzene showed no peak in ir spectrum corresponding to OH but a strong absorption at 1770 cm^{-1} (C=O). Nmr spectrum showed a peak at δ 6.2 corresponding to benzylic proton.

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